

Enabling future detector technology within ePIC at the EIC

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Abstract

The detector of the ePIC experiment at the EIC includes a wide variety of detector techniques. The different technological approaches are imposed by the EIC broad physics scope and by the nature of the collider, asymmetric in energy and beam particles, made even more challenging by the whole spectrum of ion species that will collide with electrons. Part of the detector systems are by consolidated technologies, part by novel ones, developed for the application in ePIC and largely synergistic with major coming experiments and facilities, worldwide. The ePIC detector is, therefore, both a stimulus toward innovative detector approaches and it represents a testbench for the novel technologies.

This document is to underline the added value of the ePIC detector in terms of technological development and the options of collaborative effort at large beneficial to fundamental studies at high energies.

14 1 Introduction

15 The **Electron Ion Collider (EIC)** project [ref. to EIC project document, in preparation] by the United
16 States Department of Energy and marked by a specific international character calling for worldwide contribu-
17 tions in the science and detector areas, is dedicated to the ultimate understanding of **Quantum ChromoDy-**
18 **namics (QCD)**. It is, therefore, a flagship project in the context of **physics pursued with lepton-hadron**
19 **collisions** [ref. to the DIS document, in preparation]. The broad physics scope clusters around key scientific
20 questions synthetically summarized as the origin of the nucleon mass and spin, the nucleon tomography, the
21 interaction of quarks and gluons in the nuclear medium, the quark confinement and the properties of high-
22 density gluon states. This ambitious goal requires an ambitious collider (high luminosity, variety of ion beams
23 from H to U, beam polarization and tunable center-of-mass energy) and a detector capable of coping with
24 the global physics scope by inclusive and semi-inclusive Deep Inelastic Scattering (DIS) and selected exclusive
25 channels: **the ePIC detector**. The variety of measurements, the asymmetry of the colliding beams and the
26 modulation of the phase-space in the laboratory frame with the variation of the energies and the ion species
27 require the adoption of a variety of detector technologies, including established and novel ones. Therefore,
28 **ePIC is also a unique environment for enabling future detector technologies** needed at EIC and for
29 other major worldwide facilities, in a synergistic approach towards progressing in the technological field. This
30 synergy is shown by a series of detector-technology meetings with the CERN community and the ongoing
31 ALICE-ePIC collaboration towards the novel frontier of the MAPs detector.

32 In this input document to the EPPSU 2025 process, the ePIC detector is shortly recalled, in order to
33 provide a frame to the main focus: the novel detector technologies enabled via their adoption in ePIC. The
34 application in ePIC supports and facilitates their development.

35 2 The ePIC detector

36 The detector is realized by the **ePIC Collaboration** (at present: 897 members from 177 Institutions in
37 25 countries distributed in 4 world regions, to be updated before submission) in collaboration with the EIC
38 project. It consists of a Central Detector (CD), 9.5 m long, situated at the interaction point and a set of far
39 detectors along the outgoing beam lines, which complete the small-angle acceptance. Among the far detectors,
40 the luminosity system provides measurements and monitoring of the collider luminosity.

41 Figure 1 presents a schematic view of the CD. The tracking subsystem is formed by light-weighted, high
42 space resolution silicon MAPS arranged in cylindrical and disk geometries and complemented by a set of
43 more external MPGDs also in cylindrical or pseudo-cylindrical and disk layers. The particle momenta are
44 measured thanks to tracking and a new superconducting solenoid with 1.7 T reference magnetic field. Particle
45 IDentification (PID) devices are by Cherenkov imaging counters for PID above a few GeV/c and Time-Of-
46 Flight (TOF) layers at lower energies. A proximity focusing RICH with aerogel radiator equips the backward
47 endcap, a high performance DIRC by fused silica bars provides PID in the barrel, and a dual-radiator RICH
48 making use of aerogel and gas is used in the forward endcap. AC-LGAD layers measure the timing in the
49 barrel and the forward region, while the same photosensors of the backward RICH, which are sitting in the
50 acceptance, also provide time measurement. All calorimeters make use of SiPMs as sensors. Electromagnetic
51 calorimetry is by fine granularity lead tungstate crystals in the backward, a hybrid calorimetry with imaging
52 layers and sampling by lead and scintillating fibers in the barrel and sampling by lead and tungsten powder
53 in epoxy in the forward. Hadron calorimetry is by iron and scintillator elements. In the forward, the new
54 approach of SiPM-on-tile is adopted, with a fine granularity insert in the most inner region.

55 The forward far detectors and the luminosity system make use of AC-LAGDs for tracking and lead-
56 tungsten calorimetry; the same technology of the insert of the forward hadronic calorimeter is adopted for the
57 zero-degree-calorimeter (ZDC). The far backward low Q^2 -taggers, which sit in a very high-rate region, adopt
58 the timepix4 technology.

59 Unbiased data acquisition, data selection flexibility and the parallel acquisition of data for a variety of
60 physics studies is ensured by a triggerless streaming read-out, acquisition and event reconstruction system,
61 where timing information is the key parameter for the correct association of the event information.

62 The ePIC detector will be completed and installed by 2030 and the early physics phase will start in the
63 first half of the 2030's.

Figure 1: Schematic view of the ePIC central detector.

3 Novel detector technologies in ePIC

We present a selection of novel technologies adopted for the ePIC detector, underlining the synergy of these developments with other major coming facilities and experiments in the worldwide panorama. The aggressive timelines of the EIC project and of the ePIC detector realization make the technological development for ePIC both a stimulus towards novel detector technologies and a test-bench for several among them. In the following, the examples of future applications of the novel technologies adopted in ePIC are directly extracted from "The 2021 ECFA Detector Research and Development Roadmap" [ref].

ePIC solenoid -

Low-mass flexible MAPS -

Silicon Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (MAPS) are ideally suited to meet the stringent charged-particle tracking and vertex resolution requirements at the EIC because of their high point resolution, low power dissipation, and the possibility to integrate them in a low-mass instrument. The STAR experiment pioneered their use in a collider experiment and the ALICE experiment presents the current state-of-the-art.

The ePIC Silicon Vertex Tracker (SVT) will use MAPS sensors developed in a 65 nm CMOS imaging process based-off the ALICE ITS3 development. This technology enables a high granularity and low power consumption design, and offers stitching on 300 mm wafers for the development of large area sensors.

The three inner barrel layers of the SVT will use the ALICE ITS3 safer-scale sensor, which is called MOSAIX. MOSAIX is composed of an active matrix of Repeated Sensor Units (RSUs). Twelve RSUs are stitched along the length of the sensor, giving a total length of ≈ 27 cm. Sensors with a width of three, four, and five RSUs will be used to construct the SVT inner barrel layers, L0, L1 and L2, with radii of ≈ 36 , 48, and 120 mm, respectively. The sensors will be thinned to 50 μm or less and bent to form a nearly self-supporting structure inspired by the ALICE ITS3 development, adapted to the larger EIC beampipe radius and with suitably adapted services.

The SVT outer barrel and endcap disks will cover a considerably larger active area of approximately 8 m². Considerations based on yield, cost, integration, and coverage require the use of a sensor with a smaller size than the wafer-scale sensor used in the inner barrel. These regions will use the MOSAIX sensor with modifications to reduce the size. This sensor would still be large in traditional terms and is therefore referred to as the EIC Large Area Sensor (EIC-LAS). The EIC-LAS will be one RSU wide and either 5 or 6 RSUs long. In addition to reducing the size of the sensor, the EIC-LAS will have a lower number of data links than MOSAIX to match the lower SVT data rate, reduce material associated with services, and ease integration aspects. EIC-LAS sensors will be powered in series by a constant current and a dedicated communication protocol will be used to reduce the number of slow control links from the counting room to the sensor. These functions, together with the negative sensor bias voltage, will be provided by a supporting ancillary ASIC which is under development in a 110 nm SOI process.

100 The SVT outer barrel layers will be segmented in staves. The staves are composite structures using carbon-
101 composite skins, a central carbon-composite I-beam spar and cross-ribs made of heat conducting foam. The
102 side walls will be formed by low-mass FPCs based on aluminum conductors. The SVT disks feature a two-
103 sided design with a corrugated carbon composite core. The barrel and disk structures can be used to flow
104 air for cooling internal to the structures. The staves and disks will be supported by carbon-composite global
105 supports.

106 The SVT will have an overall length approximately 2.4 m and an outer radius of approximately 0.4 m.

107 The development of MOSAIX is advanced and the timelines are dictated by the ALICE upgrade. The
108 EIC-LAS development is in progress, with time projections related to the completion of the sensor for AL-
109 ICE. The application in ePIC will represent an important step forward due to the size of the instrumented
110 surface and volume: an important consolidation to establish the stitched sensor concept for large-size systems.
111 Therefore, this effort can be regarded as a test-bench for all the future high energy electron-positron facilities,
112 the Super Tau-Charm Facility and the muon collider.

113
114 **Hybrid MPGD: μ RWELL with GEM preamplification** - Micro-Pattern Gaseous Detector (MPGD)
115 technologies have been chosen to complement the Si based tracking layers in MAPS technology of the ePIC
116 detector (Fig. 1), thanks to their capacity to cover large area at limited cost, while providing space point
117 measurements with submillimetric resolution and good timing resolution ~ 10 -20 ns. The gaseous trackers
118 are based on two MPGD technologies, the cylindrical Micromegas for the barrel inner tracker and the hybrid
119 GEM- μ RWELL technology for the barrel outer tracker and the most external layers of both electron and
120 hadron end cap trackers.

121 The hybrid GEM- μ RWELL detectors are a new concept. A GEM foil acts as a pre-amplification layer for
122 the ionization charges produced in the drift region, while the μ RWELL layer provides a second amplification
123 stage. This architecture results in high gain, which offers relevant advantages.

124 This double amplification scheme requires only moderate bias voltage across each of the amplification
125 stage to achieve a high enough gain for the detector to operate at full efficiency (≥ 97 -98%) and in a safe and
126 stable condition, also in two-dimensional strip (2D-strip) readout detectors, as it is the case in ePIC. In fact,
127 high gain capability is particularly important when using 2D-strip readout structures, where the signal is split
128 between the two planes of the readout layer.

129 Another major advantage offered by the high-gain capability is the preservation of the fine space resolution
130 for inclined particle trajectories and in non-uniform magnetic field. This is pursued at ePIC by two different
131 approaches: (1) thin drift layer for the barrel outer tracker and (2) μ TPC read-out mode for the gaseous
132 detectors in the endcaps.

- 133 1. The gap of the volume in standard MPGDs is typically 3 or 4 mm thick. This geometry results in a
134 significant deterioration of both the hit point resolution and the timing resolution when the impinging
135 particle crosses the detector at an angle larger than 15° . This is due to the negative impact of both the
136 large ionization trail left by the incoming particle in the ionization volume and the Lorentz ($E \times B$)
137 effect. In the thin-gap MPGD detector concept, the thickness of the gas volume in the drift region is
138 reduced to around 1 mm. The concept has been developed to recover the position and timing resolution
139 performance. The hybrid GEM- μ RWELL with double amplification is an essential ingredient of the
140 thin-gap MPGD detector concept that allows to compensate the reduced ionization charge produced
141 in the thin drift region. The thin-gap hybrid GEM- μ RWELL is the technology adopted for the outer
142 tracker in the barrel region of ePIC detector.
- 143 2. The reduction of the detector drift gap below 3 mm is not necessary for the disks covering pseudo-
144 rapidity regions with $|\eta| > 2$, where most of the tracks impinge the detector at angles lower than 20° .
145 The particle tracks may, however, be affected by the non-uniformity of the solenoid field at the disks
146 position. This requires additional technical solutions, such as the longitudinal reconstruction of the
147 track in μ TPC mode, to retain the position resolution necessary for reliable tracking performances. The
148 μ TPC mode also implies stringent requirements on the signal timing for each read-out strip, which are
149 presently under study.

150 The R&D studies to establish the hybrid GEM- μ RWELL technology both with thin-gap geometry and μ TPC
151 read-out mode are well advanced, while the performance needs confirmation when the novel technologies are
152 coupled to the SALSA front-end ASIC under development. The approach can be applied wherever large sur-
153 faces have to be instrumented with gaseous detector preserving space and time performance for a wide variety

of trajectory phase space and in presence of non-homogeneous magnetic field. These needs are required, for instance, for the large muon systems at HL-LHC and FCC-hh.

SiPMs as sensors for a crystal electromagnetic calorimeter - The EIC physics program requires high-precision detection and identification of the scattered electrons emitted in the electron-going direction, as well as final-state photons. The highest resolution in electromagnetic calorimeters can be provided by homogeneous materials. The preferred material radiator for the backward ECal of ePIC is lead tungstate (PWO), an extremely fast, compact, and radiation-hard scintillator providing sufficient luminescence yield (15 - 25 photoelectrons/MeV) to achieve good energy resolution. The active area consists of roughly 3000 PWO crystals extending 20 cm in the longitudinal dimension and with transverse block dimensions of 2.05 cm \times 2.05 cm matched to its Molière radius. Due to the high magnetic field in the detector area, scintillating light will be read out by Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPMs). SiPMs have developed rapidly in the last 15 years and are very attractive as a readout solution for scintillating crystals. Several challenges have prevented the use of them for high-resolution homogeneous calorimeter in the past. Firstly, their present size is relatively small compared to the radiator size, which does not allow the collection of most of the scintillating light. Secondly, the sensors need to be capable of covering a large dynamic range over more than 3 orders of magnitude when the electromagnetic shower is laterally deposited over a large number of detector modules. Therefore, the active area of the SiPM has to be composed of a sufficient number of pixels to avoid saturation. Finally, additional challenges aspects of SiPMs are their relatively high rate of dark noise, the dependence of their performance on temperature, as well as their modest radiation hardness. Recently developed sensors with very high density of pixels (10- and 15- μ m pitch) have been shown to provide a good linearity over several orders of magnitude. In order to compensate for the small sensor size, each PWO crystal in ePIC will be read by several (4 or 16) independent sensors. Linearity measurements showing 2% linearity up to 3500 photoelectrons. The effect of radiation in these SiPMs and ways to anneal its effects are currently under study.

SiPMs coupled to PWO crystal in ePIC will pave the way to the future use of high-resolution calorimeters required in all future high energy electron-positron collider and for the muon collider.

Hybrid electromagnetic calorimeter - Electromagnetic calorimetry in the barrel region of ePIC poses significant challenges due to stringent physics requirements. These include achieving electron-pion separation with a rejection factor of 10^3 – 10^4 at low momenta, energy resolution better than $10\%/\sqrt{E} \oplus 1 - 2\%$ for photon reconstruction, and π^0 - γ separation up to 10 GeV. Additionally, the system must measure low-energy photons down to 100 MeV while operating within the constrained space inside the solenoid.

Traditional approaches, such as PbWO₄ crystals or Shashlyk calorimeters, cannot meet these demands due to limitations in material availability, cost, or inadequate electron-pion separation, particularly given the radial space constraints. To overcome these challenges, ePIC uses a hybrid barrel electromagnetic calorimeter, the Barrel Imaging Calorimeter (BIC), that combines scintillating fiber and lead (Pb/ScFi) sampling layers, based on the GlueX BCAL design pioneered at KLOE, with layers of highly-granular silicon sensors AstroPix.

AstroPix is a low-power monolithic active pixel sensor (HV-MAPS) with a 500 μ m pixel pitch, derived from ATLASPix and developed by Karlsruhe Institute of Technology in collaboration with NASA-GSFC and Argonne National Laboratory for space-based applications (as part of the NASA AMEGO-X program). This sensor is an ideal fit for the barrel electromagnetic calorimeter, providing the necessary spatial granularity and excellent energy resolution, along with sufficient time resolution for 3D shower imaging.

The hybrid design enables the detector to meet all of the EIC's stringent requirements, including achieving an energy resolution of approximately $5.2\%/\sqrt{E} \oplus 1.0\%$. The ePIC Barrel Imaging Calorimeter (BIC) represents one of the largest silicon detectors ever constructed and marks the first large-scale application of HV-CMOS technology for particle detection. Key challenges include scaling production to cover and test over 100 m² of silicon sensors and reconstructing the volumes of data generated by the granular hybrid system to fully utilize their multidimensional character. Recent beam and bench tests have demonstrated the calorimeter's readiness to meet the demands of the EIC physics program while advancing detector technologies for future experiments at all high-energy electron-positron colliders and at the muon collider.

W/SciFi electromagnetic calorimeter - Fiber calorimeters have been in use in high-energy and nuclear physics experiments for nearly 40 years, standing out as some of the finest sampling calorimeters in operation. They offer excellent energy resolution, granularity, hermeticity, and homogeneity, along with precise timing and position resolution—all achievable within highly compact designs. This technology is particularly well-

209 suited to leverage advancements in compact photodetectors such as APDs and SiPMs. These qualities make
210 fiber calorimeters an attractive choice for the ePIC central detector.

211 However, traditional construction techniques for such calorimeters have been labor-intensive and somewhat
212 limiting, especially when building compact calorimeters with good energy resolution. These designs require
213 managing large quantities of thin scintillating fibers, finely spaced within absorber materials. To address
214 these challenges, a new technology utilizing tungsten (W) powder as an absorber was developed through
215 the generic detector R&D program for the EIC. This innovation simplifies the construction processes and it
216 was specifically designed for easily adoption by university groups: in fact, it does not require infrastructure
217 investment.

218 The W/ScFi technology, pioneered at UCLA, has proven to be remarkably straightforward, enabling its
219 rapid adoption across US universities, as well as institutions in China, Europe, and India among the ePIC
220 collaborators. Notably, the sPHENIX barrel EMCal, consisting of approximately 25,000 readout towers, was
221 recently constructed using this technique and is now operational at RHIC.

222 For the ePIC detector, this technology will be deployed in the hadron endcap, maximizing all its ad-
223 vantageous properties. Featuring SiPM readout, the calorimeter achieves about 23 radiation lengths within
224 only 27 cm of integration space along the beamline. It is expected to be one of the most compact sampling
225 calorimeters featuring such parameters ever constructed. As it is the case for other calorimetry technologies
226 pioneered for application at the EIC, the W/SciFi electromagnetic calorimeter approach will contribute in
227 advancing detector technologies for future experiments at all high-energy electron-positron colliders and at
228 the muon collider.

229 **SiPM-on-tile hadron calorimeter -**

231 **AC-LGADs** - The AC-LGAD (AC-coupled Low Gain Avalanche Detector/Diode) is a new type of semi-
232 conductor detector that incorporates an AC-coupled electrode into a conventional LGAD structure, thereby
233 achieving high spatial resolution and reduced dead area in addition to excellent timing performance. LGADs
234 feature a strong internal electric-field multiplication region, which efficiently amplifies charges and provides
235 time resolutions on the order of tens of picoseconds. However, conventional LGADs suffer from limited spatial
236 resolution and dead zones because each pixel requires a separate readout electrode. Overcoming this “ac-
237 ceptance hole” typically necessitates a multilayer design, which increases both the material budget and the
238 required installation space. AC-LGADs address these challenges by coupling the readout electrode to the
239 signal layer through an insulating layer. This design effectively eliminates acceptance holes by removing the
240 gaps between electrodes. This architecture also enables charge sharing among adjacent electrodes, signifi-
241 cantly improving spatial resolution. As a result, a single-layer configuration becomes feasible, reducing the
242 total material and creating a more compact detector with improved performance. These advantages make
243 AC-LGADs an attractive choice for tracking and timing layers in future large collider experiments, offering
244 high time and spatial resolution with minimal interference for other detectors, even when the experimental
245 space is limited.

246 In recent years, the ePIC collaboration has been actively developing this new technology for practical
247 applications. The collaboration plans to employ it for particle identification in the low- p_T region. The
248 collaboration is exploring various electrode designs, such as strip and pixel types, to accommodate different
249 particle multiplicities. Specifically, strip detectors will cover the mid-rapidity region, while pixel detectors will
250 be used in the forward-rapidity region. Time resolutions below 35 ps and spatial resolutions better than 30
251 μm have already been achieved. Going forward, the ePIC collaboration will continue to enhance the sensor
252 performance and move toward an engineered design, aiming to deploy this technology as a fully operational
253 detector.

254 The ongoing research and development of AC-LGAD-based sensors will play an essential role in advancing
255 particle physics experiments. This technology, when fully mature, will complete the ePIC detector and it
256 can contribute to particle identification in the HI-LHC era at ALICE and LHCb, while also supporting the
257 tracking systems of these experiments.

258 **Photosensors for Cherenkov imaging counters**

259 **HRPPDs** - Vacuum-based photodetectors are since the early days of Cherenkov detectors a privileged choice
260 for the sensors thanks to the option of efficient photoconverters in the visible range, where radiator chromatic
261 effects are moderate, and to the low dark count rate. The increasing request of operating in magnetic field
262

264 limits the usage of traditional PhotoMultiplier Tubes (PMTs), while opening the way to MicroChannel Plate
265 (MCP) PMTs, more tolerant to magnetic field. So far, they have been adopted only in the TOP counter of
266 the BELLE II experiment. Commercial MCP-PMTs, produced by a few companies, are small size ones, never
267 overcoming the 2 in² surface. The novel large-size sensors by INCOM [footnote with INCOM address] offer a
268 unique opportunity to overcome the current limitations. The development and engineering of these detectors
269 is by a cooperative academia-industry effort. In recent year, ePIC has played a major role in cooperating
270 to this development. HRPPDs are characterized by a sensitive area of 10.4×10.4 cm², a limited dead-area
271 of 25%, the quantum efficiency of high-quality PMTs, excellent timing resolution as good as 15 ps for single
272 photoelectron signals and expected life of a few C/cm². HRPPDs represent a concrete option for Cherenkov
273 imaging counters. In ePIC, they will be used in the backward proximity focusing RICH and are considered
274 as sensors for the high performance DIRC. The extended usage in ePIC will provide consolidated confidence
275 in the industrial process and in the sensor reliability. The R&D to develop HRPPDs is completed and the
276 engineering phase is advanced. A major challenge for further applications is preserving the industrial interest
277 beyond the dedicated production series for ePIC.

278 **SiPMs** - Silicon Photo Multipliers (SiPM), introduced towards the end of the 20th century for application
279 in fundamental research, are nowadays largely used in a much wider domain including applications of social
280 interest. The trend suggests that SiPMs are going to dominate the worldwide panorama of photodetectors in
281 fundamental research and beyond. Their application as single photon sensors in Cherenkov imaging devices
282 has been considered for 20 years and never adopted due to the dark count rate, where background signals are
283 intrinsically indistinguishable from single photon signals. These rates substantially increase by radiation dam-
284 age. An extended and robust R&D program, conducted within ePIC for the application of SiPMs in the dual
285 RICH, has proven that thermal annealing cycles can, to a large extent, recover the damage, also in repeated
286 cycles of irradiation/annealing and that thermal annealing is conceivable in place applying reversed bias to
287 the sensors. This approach, combined with low temperature operation and hit selection by fine timestamp,
288 qualifies SiPMs for the application in Cherenkov imaging counters. The usage in ePIC dual RICH will prove
289 the validity of the approach and it will open the way to further progress related to the expected advancement
290 and novel development in the field of SiPMs. The R&D for the usage of SiPMs as single photon detectors is
291 completed and the engineering phase is advanced. Applying these concepts to novel SiPMs technologies as
292 the 3-D SiPMs is being considered as a potential path forward in the approach.

293 Novel or upgraded RICH detectors are foreseen for ALICE3, LHCb, BELLE II, the fix target program
294 at CERN and considered as an option for FCC-ee. When completely established as single photon sensors,
295 HRPPDs and SiPMs can be selected for a large number of these programs. Therefore, by qualifying these
296 technologies for ePIC RICHes, the ePIC. collaboration is paving the way towards the approach to single pho-
297 ton detection for the next generation of Cherenkov imaging devices.

299 **New frontend ASICs with triggerless architecture: EICROC, CALOROC, FCFD, SALSA, AL-** 300 **COR -**

301 A new generation of frontend ASICs are being developed for ePIC. They support the specific requirements
302 of the different sensor technologies, while designed so to satisfy the prescriptions for triggerless operation and
303 streaming readout. To this end all these frontend ASICs, a part ALCOR, include output links with rate
304 capability, greater than 1 Gbps. In ALCOR, the requirement of high throughput bandwidth is attacked with
305 a different strategy, namely multiple links of 788 Mbps. The ASICs are shortly described in the following.

306 **EICROC** – The EICROC is designed for the readout of the AC-LGAD pixels, arranged in a 32x32 ma-
307 trix and implemented in a wafer-bumped, 130 nm CMOS technology node and featuring radiation tolerant.
308 Preamp, discriminator, TOA, ADC and TDC are included for sensors with capacitance of up to 5 pF and
309 timing precision better than 30 ps. The power dissipation of less than 2 mW per channel.

310 **CALOROC** – The CALOROC is applicable to the readout of SiPMs in calorimeters. It consists of 64
311 channels implemented in a BGA-packaged, 130 nm CMOS technology node and it is radiation tolerant. In
312 addition, to facilities the bias trimming of the SiPM channels, it includes ADCs, TOTs and TOAs for sensor
313 with capacities up to 10 nF and dynamic range up to 12 nC. The power dissipation lower than 10 mW per
314 channel.

315 **FCFD** – The FCFD will be coupled to the AC-LGAD strips with 128 channels. It is implemented in a
316 65 nm CMOS technology node for wire-bonding to sensors and it is radiation tolerant. It includes constant
317 fraction discriminators, TDCs and ADCs and supports sensors with capacitance up to 15 pF. The timing
318 precision is better than 30 ps.

319 SALSA – The SALSA ASIC, 64 channels, is designed to readout MPGDs. It is implemented in a BGA-
320 packaged, 65 nm CMOS technology node and it is radiation tolerant. In addition to extensive facilities for
321 data processing, it supports readout from detector with capacitance up to 200 pF and offers a dynamic range
322 of up to 250 fC, multiple selectable shaping parameters down to signals as short as 50 ns, dual polarity and
323 12-bit ADCs. The power dissipation of less than 15 mW per channel.

324 ALCOR - The ALCOR is designed for the readout of SiPMs where sensitivity to single photo-electron
325 is required, and specific to the dRICH detector in ePIC. It consists of 64 channels implemented in a BGA-
326 packaged, 110 nm CMOS technology node and it is radiation tolerant. In addition to facilities for bias
327 trimming of SiPM channels, it includes amplification, conditioning, TDCs, inhibit and digitization for single-
328 photon tagging or selection based on time and charge. The timing precision is better than 150 ps. The inhibit
329 functions as a shutter to decrease the impact of SiPM dark rates. The power dissipation of less than 12 mW
330 per channel.

331 These ASICs are at various stages of development with IP blocks being tested making use of Multiple
332 Project Wafer (MPW) runs. The final designs will be submitted for fabrication by 2027 and following the
333 final design reviews.

334 The development of five new frontend chips adequate for modern triggerless read-out and data acquisition
335 chains, designed for different detector families, namely tracking by MPGDs, calorimetry read-out by SiPMs,
336 timing and tracking with AC-LGADS with pixel and strip arrangements, and the novel application of SiPMs
337 for single photon detection in Cherenkov imaging devices, offers to the whole community dedicated to funda-
338 mental research in particle and nuclear physics a rich contribution of up-to-date building blocks to design the
339 readout in the next generation of experiment upgrades and new experimental efforts.

340 **Homogenous approach in streaming read-out/DAQ/data analysis and computing -**

341 The ePIC detector is characterized by high channel counts ($\sim 16e9$ pixels, and $\sim 8e6$ digitized channels),
342 high rates (~ 500 kHz), and low occupancy (~ 25 kB/event). The development of streaming ASICs coupled
343 with high rate fiber and network resources offers the possibility of reading all hit data into commercially
344 available computing. While there are significant custom electronics remaining in the system in the readout,
345 aggregation, and data transfer stages of the DAQ, this bypasses the need for the complexity and expense of
346 a traditional hardware based trigger system. Moving processing tasks from custom electronics to computing
347 decreases cost and increases flexibility as regards programming tools, algorithms, and hardware.

348 The streaming design allows the minimization of selection bias in analysis by ensuring that the event
349 selection can be performed using the full detector readout. It operates with no global dead-time, and offers
350 unprecedented characterization of detector background and noise. Streaming designs are more susceptible to
351 backgrounds and noise than triggered systems. This will require accurate evaluation of beam backgrounds
352 as part of the design as well as high-level filters that can be applied in both during the aggregation of data
353 by FPGA and in DAQ computer employing CPU and GPU algorithms. These algorithms can be based on
354 standard triggering concepts or else utilize ML techniques.

355 Along with the streaming DAQ, computing is an integral part of the experimental data pipeline. It serves
356 two prominent roles: (1) data reduction: unlike the traditional DAQ, which utilizes real-time triggering for
357 data reduction, the streaming DAQ performs data reduction computationally to store all collision signals and
358 to minimize selection biases. This step includes feature building, high-level filtering, and lossy compression
359 to allow data to fit into the persistent storage bandwidth. The echelon 0 computing facility, which is located
360 at and near the experiment with exclusively controlled computing resources, is envisioned to serve this role.
361 (2) Prompt reconstruction: We envision the ePIC data being promptly transferred for processing at echelon-
362 1 computing facilities located at the host laboratories (BNL and JLab), which allows for rapid feedback to
363 operation and for physics analysis with fully reconstructed data. A key component that determines the latency
364 of the reconstruction is an automated calibration pipeline that buffers collision data and performs automated
365 multi-iteration calibration processing based on the needs of the diverse set of detector subsystems in ePIC.

366 The concept of streaming read-out/DAQ/data analysis is already under development and in operation in
367 other experiments, as, for instance, the LHC ALICE and LHCb. The implementations are, in the various
368 applications, optimized for the specific needs. ePIC will provide one more approach, fully comprehensive and
369 based on a design of the read-out/DAQ/data analysis/computing chain which is conceived for streaming since
370 its initial design. Therefore, these developments, which are critical for maximizing the physics output at ePIC,
371 also provide synergy with global experimental efforts such as LHC experiments and BELLE II.

374 **Novel approaches to synchrotron radiation simulation -**

375 Synchrotron radiation (SR) is an intrinsic consequence of charged particle acceleration in magnetic fields,
376 playing a dual role in colliders. While essential for beam diagnostics, it presents significant challenges, par-
377 ticularly in high-luminosity machines like the EIC. The intense SR emitted by beams can generate secondary
378 particles, elevate background levels in detectors, and cause localized heating and damage to machine compo-
379 nents, including vacuum chambers and magnets. These effects pose a critical barrier to achieving the precise
380 measurements required for the ePIC experiment's exploration of QCD and hadronic structure.

381 To address these challenges, SynradG4 [A. Natochii, 2024] has been developed recently at BNL, a novel
382 simulation framework built on Geant4, tailored for comprehensive modeling of SR impacts. SynradG4 inte-
383 grates advanced photon transport and interaction models with high-resolution beam dynamics inputs, enabling
384 precise predictions of SR-induced particle showers and their effects on both the detector and the machine. By
385 leveraging detailed beam optics to track charged particles through the machine lattice accurately, SynradG4
386 provides a unique platform to evaluate and mitigate SR's detrimental impacts.

387 The framework incorporates several novel elements, including enhanced modeling of photon-material in-
388 teractions and a high-precision approach to simulating the generation and transport of SR photons using the
389 Geant4 libraries [S. Agostinelli et al., 2003; J. Allison et al., 2006; J. Allison et al., 2016]. These innovations
390 allow for a more accurate representation of the spatial and temporal characteristics of SR effects within the
391 interaction region. SynradG4 is validated against alternative, experimentally verified simulation tools, offering
392 confidence in its predictive capabilities.

393 Despite its readiness, scaling SynradG4 simulations to the EIC's full lattice complexity and integrating
394 machine-specific phenomena like SR masking and radiation shielding remains an active area of development.
395 Close collaboration between machine and detector experts will be essential to address these challenges, ensuring
396 SynradG4 fulfills its role in safeguarding machine components and optimizing detector performance. This effort
397 positions SynradG4 as a critical tool for enabling precision physics in the next generation of colliders.

398 **4 Messages**

399 A wide set of novel technologies are adopted for the ePIC detector, which are largely synergistic with the
400 requirements of other major coming facilities and experiments in the worldwide panorama. The timelines
401 of the ePIC detector realization make these technological developments a stimulus towards novel detector
402 approaches and an opportunity for test-benching.

403 The technologies considered in this document include the ePIC solenoid, the novel light-weighted flexible
404 Si tracker, μ RWELL with GEM preamplification, a hybrid electromagnetic calorimeter with imaging layers and
405 sampling by lead and scintillating fibers, the approach to electromagnetic calorimetry by tungsten powder and
406 scintillating fibers, hadron calorimetry by SiPM-on-tile approach, the extended usage of AC-LGADs, two novel
407 approaches for photosensors in Cherenkov imaging devices, a set of novel front-end ASICs, the homogenous
408 approach in streaming read-out/DAQ/data analysis and computing and novel tools for synchrotron radiation
409 simulation.

410 Synergies with the experiments at HL-LHC, at FCC, at the muon collider, at BELLE II and for the future
411 fix-target program at CERN are self-evident and have been specifically underlined, technology by technology.
412 A common effort towards the development and validation of these technologies is mutually beneficial to
413 these experimental programs and to ePIC. In this perspective, ePIC represents an opportunity of worldwide
414 technological progress for fundamental research at high energy.

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